

Synthesis and biological evaluation of 1,2,4-oxadiazole linked imidazopyrazine derivatives as anticancer agents

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Abstract: A series of new 1,2,4-oxadiazole linked imidazopyrazines (**10a-j**) were synthesized and evaluated for their cytotoxic activity against various human cancer cell lines, such as MCF-7 (breast), A549 (lung), and A375 (melanoma). These compounds showed moderate to appreciable anticancer activities. Among them, compounds **10b**, **10c**, **10d**, **10f** and **10i** were showed more potent activity than adriamycin.

Keywords: Imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine, phidianidines A, B and cytotoxicity.

INTRODUCTION

Recent literature reveals that small heterocyclic frameworks, such as nitrogen heterocycles, offer an advantage in designing of antiproliferative agents as they mimic many biomolecules. Imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (**1**) was a nitrogen containing heterocyclic that have been gain consideration in drug discovery realm especially as structural analogues of purines.¹⁻³ Imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine derivatives were showed a different biological activities such as antiproliferative activity,⁴ Aurora-A kinase inhibitors,⁵ antiulcer,⁶ antibacterial,⁷ anti-inflammatory,⁸ uterine relaxing activity,⁹ antibronchospastic,¹⁰ cardiac stimulating,¹¹ antidepressant,¹² hypoglycemic activity,¹³ controlling allergic reactions.¹⁴ Recently some of the imidazopyrazine derivatives were reported as anticancer activity.⁵

Heterocyclic compounds are very important class of organic compounds and in particular 1,2,4-oxadiazoles are prominent targets for synthetic chemists primarily because of

their diverse and potent biological properties.¹⁵ These have been showed a wide range of biological properties, such as antitumor,¹⁶ antimicrobial,¹⁷ analgesic,¹⁸ antiasthmatic,¹⁹ diuretic,²⁰ antidiabetic,²¹ anthelmintic,²² anti-inflammatory,²³ anti-HIV²⁴ and antiparasitic,²⁵ activities. Recently two novel 1,2,4-oxadiazole alkaloids phidianidines A (**2**) and B (**3**) (Figure 1), had been isolated from the shell-less marine opisthobranch mollusk *Phidiana militaris*²⁶ which were showed strong antitumor activity against C6 and HeLa cells with the IC₅₀ values within nanomolar range.²⁷⁻²⁹

In view of the above information of both moieties and continuation of efforts, we have designed the synthesis of 1,2,4-oxadiazole-linked imidazopyrazine derivatives and characterized their ¹HNMR, ¹³CNMR and Mass spectral data. Further these derivatives were evaluated for their anticancer activity on human cancer cell lines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

All chemicals and reagents were obtained from Aldrich (Sigma–Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), Lancaster (Alfa Aesar, Johnson Matthey Company, Ward Hill, MA, USA) and were used without further purification. Reactions were monitored by TLC, performed on silica gel glass plates containing 60 F-254, and visualization on TLC was achieved by UV light or iodine indicator. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker, Bruker UXNMR/XWIN-NMR (500 MHz, 400 MHz, 300 MHz) instrument. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in ppm downfield from internal TMS standard. ESI spectra were recorded on Micro mass, Quattro LC using ESI+ software with capillary voltage 3.98 kV and ESI mode positive ion trap detector. Melting points were determined with an electrothermal melting point apparatus, and are uncorrected.

(E)-N,N-Dimethyl-N'-(pyrazin-2-yl)formamidine (**6**)

N,N-Dimethylformamide dimethyl acetal (8.3 mL, 63.15 mmol) was added to a solution of pyrazine-2-amine (5 g, 52.6 mmol) in methanol (30 mL), and the mixture was refluxed for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, concentrated and evaporated to afford pure compound **6** in 7.82 g with 99% yield. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.10 (s, 6H), 8.06 (d, 1H, $J = 2.7$ Hz), 8.10 (dd, 1H, $J = 2.7$ Hz), 8.27 (d, 1H, $J = 1.4$ Hz), 8.41 (s, 1H); MS (ESI): 151 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$.

Imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine-3-carbonitrile (8)

In a 20 mL clean round bottom flask, (E)-N,N-dimethyl-N'-(pyrazin-2-yl)formamidine (**6**) (7 g, 46.6 mmol) was dissolved in isopropanol (30 mL), added 2-bromoacetonitrile (3.2 mL, 46.6 mmol), NaHCO_3 (23.4 g, 279 mmol) and the mixture was heated at 100°C for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, concentrated and evaporated and this crude compound was purified by column chromatography with ethyl acetate/hexane (3:7) to afford pure compound **8** in 4.6 g with 68% yield. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d_6): δ 7.91 (d, 1H, $J = 8.25$ Hz), 8.21 (d, 1H, $J = 8.21$ Hz), 8.28 (s, 1H), 8.37 (s, 1H); MS (ESI): 145 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$.

General Procedure for the synthesis of 1,2,4-oxadiazole linked imidazopyrazines (10a-j):

In a 5-mL round-bottom flask, imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine-3-carbonitrile (**8**) (2.08 mmol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (144 mg, 2.08 mmol), and benzoic acid (**9a-j**) (2.08 mmol) were added to 4-(dimethylamino) pyridinium acetate (4.16 mmol). The reaction mixture was heated to 100°C for 6 hours. The mixture is cooled to room temperature, ethanol (1 mL) was added, and stirring continued for 30 min. Next, water (5 mL) was added to the reaction mixture. The ionic liquid was dissolved in water and filtered for separation of the products. The solid products were collected and washed twice with water (2×5 mL). The crude product was purified by column chromatography with hexanes/ethyl acetate to afford pure compounds (10a-j).

3-(5-Phenyl-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (10a)

57% yield. Mp: $138\text{--}140^\circ\text{C}$, ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d_6): δ 7.38-7.49 (m, 3H), 7.56 (d, 1H, $J = 8.15$ Hz), 7.69 (d, 1H, $J = 8.15$ Hz), 7.85 (d, 2H, $J = 8.34$ Hz), 8.29 (s, 1H), 8.41 (s, 1H); ^{13}C

NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 0.3, 116.4, 117.6, 126.5, 127.6, 129.4, 131.4, 132.5, 134.6, 138.7, 139.8, 143.5, 160.5; MS (ESI): 264 [M+H]⁺.

3-(5-(3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (10b)

44% yield. Mp: 162-164°C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 3.86 (s, 3H), 3.94 (s, 6H), 7.55 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.14 Hz), 7.69 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.14 Hz), 7.74 (s, 2H), 8.29 (s, 1H), 8.40 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 58.5, 62.7, 90.4, 104.6, 116.7, 117.6, 126.4, 128.6, 132.6, 138.6, 139.6, 143.5, 145.8, 154.8, 160.6; MS (ESI): 354 [M+H]⁺.

3-(5-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (10c)

54% yield. Mp: 147-149°C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 3.86 (s, 3H), 7.23 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.34 Hz), 7.57 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.17 Hz), 7.69 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.17 Hz), 7.86 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.34 Hz), 8.29 (s, 1H), 8.42 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 57.5, 90.5, 114.7, 116.7, 117.9, 126.7, 127.7, 131.6, 132.6, 138.6, 138.9, 143.7, 160.6, 163.7; MS (ESI): 294 [M+H]⁺.

3-(5-(4-Chlorophenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (10d)

57% yield. Mp: 163-165°C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 7.58 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.19 Hz), 7.63 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.33 Hz), 7.70 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.19 Hz), 7.82 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.33 Hz), 8.30 (s, 1H), 8.43 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 90.7, 116.8, 117.8, 126.7, 127.6, 129.6, 132.5, 134.5, 135.7, 138.6, 139.6, 143.6, 160.8; MS (ESI): 298 [M+H]⁺.

3-(5-(4-Bromophenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (10e)

50% yield. Mp: 161-163°C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 7.59 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.20 Hz), 7.65-7.84 (m, 3H), 8.30 (s, 1H), 8.43 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 90.8, 116.8, 117.9, 124.7, 126.7, 127.9, 132.6, 133.5, 133.8, 138.6, 139.7, 143.6, 160.7; MS (ESI): 343 [M+H]⁺.

3-(5-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (10f)

58% yield. Mp: 144-146°C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 7.34 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.38 Hz), 7.58 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.18 Hz), 7.68 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.18 Hz), 7.81 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.38 Hz), 7.28 (s, 1H), 8.41 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 90.5, 116.8, 117.7, 119.7, 126.7, 128.6, 128.9, 130.7, 132.7, 138.5, 139.8, 143.6, 154.8, 160.5; MS (ESI): 282 [M+H]⁺.

3-(5-(4-Nitrophenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (10g)

64% yield. Mp: 170-172°C, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 7.59 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.20 Hz), 7.69 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.20 Hz), 7.73 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.37 Hz), 7.79 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.37 Hz), 8.30 (s, 1H), 8.43 (s,

1H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 90.8, 116.8, 117.9, 125.8, 126.7, 127.8, 132.6, 138.6, 139.8, 141.6, 143.5, 148.7, 160.8; MS (ESI): 309 [M+H]⁺.

3-(5-p-Tolyl-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (10h)

55% yield. Mp: 137-139°C, ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 2.54 (s, 3H), 7.19 (d, 2H, $J = 8.24$ Hz), 7.57 (d, 1H, $J = 8.16$ Hz), 7.67 (d, 1H, $J = 8.16$ Hz), 7.76 (d, 2H, $J = 8.24$ Hz), 8.28 (s, 1H), 8.40 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 23.6, 90.4, 116.5, 117.6, 125.6, 126.7, 127.6, 132.5, 133.6, 137.6, 138.5, 139.6, 143.5, 160.3; MS (ESI): 278 [M+H]⁺.

4-(3-(Imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazin-3-yl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)benzotrile (10i)

70% yield. Mp: 164-166°C, ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 7.60 (d, 1H, $J = 8.21$ Hz), 7.69 (d, 1H, $J = 8.21$ Hz), 7.78 (d, 2H, $J = 8.35$ Hz), 7.83 (d, 2H, $J = 8.35$ Hz), 8.30 (s, 1H), 8.42 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 90.7, 114.5, 116.7, 117.8, 119.7, 125.7, 126.8, 132.6, 136.7, 138.6, 139.8, 140.6, 143.6, 160.81 MS (ESI): 289 [M+H]⁺.

3-(5-(4-(Trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine (10j)

46% yield. Mp: 156-158°C, ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 7.57 (d, 1H, $J = 8.15$ Hz), 7.67 (d, 1H, $J = 8.15$ Hz), 7.74 (d, 2H, $J = 8.28$ Hz), 7.82 (d, 2H, $J = 8.28$ Hz), 8.27 (s, 1H), 8.40 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 90.6, 114.6, 116.7, 117.9, 126.8, 127.9, 128.6, 132.5, 133.5, 135.6, 138.6, 139.8, 143.6, 160.7; MS (ESI): 332 [M+H]⁺.

MTT Assay:

The cytotoxic activity of the compounds was determined using MTT assay. 1×10^4 cells/well were seeded in 200 mL DMEM, supplemented with 10% FBS in each well of 96-well microculture plates and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C in a CO₂ incubator. Compounds, diluted to the desired concentrations in culture medium, were added to the wells with respective vehicle control. After 48 hours of incubation, 10 mL MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) (5 mg/mL) was added to each well and the plates were further incubated for 4 hours. Then the supernatant from each well was carefully removed, formazon crystals were dissolved in 100 mL of DMSO and absorbance at 540 nm wavelength was recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of 1,2,4-oxadiazole linked imidazopyrazine derivatives (**10a-j**) is shown in Scheme 1. The pyrazin-2-amine (**4**) was reacted with dimethoxy-N,N-dimethylmethanamine (DMF-DMA)(**5**) in methanol and refluxed for 6 hours to afford pure (E)-N,N-dimethyl-N'-(pyrazin-2-

yl)formamidine (**6**) in good yield. This intermediate **6** was cyclized with 2-bromoacetonitrile (**7**) in isopropanol, NaHCO₃ at 100 °C for 6 hours to afford pure compound imidazo[1,2-a]pyrazine-3-carbonitrile (**8**). The cyano intermediate (**8**) was cyclized with different substituted aromatic carboxylic acids (**9a-j**) in 4-(dimethylamino) pyridinium acetate, NH₂OH.HCl at 100 °C for 6 hours to afford pure compounds **10a-j**.

Scheme 1.

Biological Evaluation

In Vitro Cytotoxicity

These newly synthesized 1,2,4-oxadiazole linked imidazopyrazine compounds (**10a-j**) were evaluated for their in vitro anticancer activity against a panel of three human cancer cell lines, MCF-7 (breast), A549 (lung), and A375 (melanoma) by employing MTT assay and adriamycin was taken as positive control, results are summarized in Table-1 and expressed as IC₅₀(μM) values. The in vitro screening results revealed that some of the compounds possess considerable anticancer activity. Among them, compounds **10b**, **10c**, **10d**, **10f** and **10i** were showed more potent activity than adriamycin.

Table-1 Cytotoxic activity of compounds **10a-j** in (IC₅₀μM)

Compound	MCF-7	A549	A375
10a	2.10±0.15	3.56±0.18	4.90±0.27
10b	0.68±0.03	1.56±0.061	0.79±0.033
10c	2.11±0.14	1.02±0.043	0.34±0.016
10d	1.45±0.06	0.90±0.032	2.18±0.112
10e	19.7±0.83	14.6±0.86	21.5±0.688
10f	1.35±0.058	0.55±0.001	1.67±0.06
10g	12.3±0.43	5.3±0.25	4.8±0.218
10h	10.6±0.53	13.4±0.68	8.6±0.52
10i	0.22±0.009	1.09±0.041	1.18±0.054
10j	2.44±0.12	3.89±0.151	10.5±0.56
Doxorubicin	2.02±0.078	2.18±0.081	5.51±0.203

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have been synthesized a series of 1,2,4-oxadiazole linked imidazopyrazine derivatives (**10a-j**) and these were characterized by ¹HNMR, ¹³CNMR and mass spectroscopic data. Further these compounds were evaluated for their anticancer activity on three different types of human cancer cell line (MCF-7 (breast), A549 (lung), and A375 (melanoma)). Among them, compounds **10b**, **10c**, **10d**, **10f** and **10i** were showed more potent activity than adriamycin.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to express our gratitude and thanks to Department of Chemistry, ICFAI Foundation for Higher Education, Hyderabad, for providing facilities and carrying out the research.

CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS

All authors have none to declare

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